

Group Theory and Geometry in Music

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1 Introduction

This paper examines the mathematical nature of music, focusing on how scales can be represented algorithmically and geometrically. It primarily considers Indian music, specifically Carnatic *ragas* (the Western analogue being scales), while also comparing them with Western scales. It introduces the notions of *even* and *deep* scales, which are then used to classify ragas and scales by the emotions they evoke when played, thereby seeking a connection between the apparently disparate worlds of music and mathematics.

The paper [1] introduces two central concepts that form the foundation of its arguments and conclusions: *evenness* and *deepness*.

Evenness is relatively intuitive: it refers to the property of maximally well-spaced intervals in rhythms or scales. According to the authors, rhythms exhibiting a higher degree of evenness are more prevalent across traditional musical practices worldwide.

Deepness, by contrast, is less straightforward. The authors distinguish between two types of deepness:

1. *Erdős-deep*
2. *Winograd-deep*

To interpret these definitions properly, it is necessary first to understand how musical rhythms and scales are represented geometrically.

The paper defines a rhythm or scale on a circle with circumference n . Since there are theoretically infinitely many points on the circumference, a rhythm can be considered a subset of these points; this subset is denoted by k , representing the number of onsets or pitches in a rhythm or scale, respectively [1].

Erdős-deep refers to a property of musical rhythms or scales in which any distance (i.e., the arc length between two onsets on the circle) must occur with a unique multiplicity (the number of occurrences). More rigorously, a rhythm or scale with k onsets is Erdős-deep if, for every multiplicity $(1, 2, \dots, k - 1)$, there exists a non-zero arc length or geodesic distance determined by the points on the circle with exactly that multiplicity [1].

Winograd-deep refers to a property wherein all distances between 1 and $n/2$ occur with unique multiplicity. In other words, every distance $(1, 2, \dots, n/2)$ must have a unique number of occurrences.

The authors employ these definitions to demonstrate a connection between Euclid’s algorithm and even and deep rhythms, with particular reference to both Western and traditional world music. While their study touches on a wide range of global rhythmic traditions, it leaves two aspects largely unexplored:

1. The analysis of deepness and evenness is conducted exclusively for rhythms. Although the extension of these concepts to scales is briefly mentioned, it is not explicitly developed.
2. The work does not examine any specific musical genre in detail, as the emphasis is instead on illustrating cross-cultural connections.

In this study, we focus on how *deepness* correlates with the prevalence and perceived consonance of Carnatic scales. Our emphasis on deepness, rather than evenness, arises from the fact that evenness in scales is already understood to be strongly associated with harmonic appeal and widespread preference. By contrast, the role of deepness is less clear, particularly in the context of Carnatic music, which differs significantly from Western traditions.

In summary, the present work investigates whether deepness is a characteristic feature of Carnatic ragas (the analogues of Western scales), and whether it accounts for their prominence as well as their harmonic and aesthetic appeal.

2 Literature Review

This paper borrows definitions and representations from the original source, and therefore, it is important to define and understand them. From this point forward, we will no longer refer to rhythms and will instead focus solely on musical scales.

2.1 Representation

As noted above, the geometric and mathematical representation of a musical scale is given by a circle with circumference n and a specific subset of k points on it, each point representing a note in the scale. This representation allows the scale to be cyclic (since musical scales are naturally repetitive and patterned), while also providing a visual aid and a basis for all subsequent algorithms and definitions. Furthermore, another prominent representation borrowed from the paper is binary, in the form of *dots* and *crosses*. A musical scale can be compared with a binary system in which 0 represents a silence/rest and 1 represents a played note/pitch. For visual clarity, 0s are replaced with dots ‘.’ and 1s with crosses ‘×’. (Refer to Figure (3))

Next is the concept of **Depth**. To recap the definitions: Winograd-deep scales are those in which *every possible* distance that can occur in that scale does occur, each with a unique multiplicity. Erdős-deep scales are those in which *any* distance that does occur in that scale must occur with a unique multiplicity.

It is evident that every Winograd-deep scale is automatically Erdős-deep, but an Erdős-deep scale need not be Winograd-deep.

2.2 Findings

The paper uses these definitions to conclude that the world rhythms it considers (widely used in traditional settings) are both maximally even and deep. It first proves that Euclidean rhythms are both deep and even and then shows their prevalence in various musical contexts.

However, the present work addresses the connection between depth and aesthetic preference, principally using the definitions of depth to create an algorithm that decides whether a scale is deep. We apply this to Carnatic ragas and then attempt to find a correlation.

3 Methodology

3.1 Definitions

In this study, scales and ragas are represented as binary sequences, bidirectional and theoretically infinite in nature, where each bit corresponds to a distinct note or tone within the scale. A value of one indicates the presence of a note (an onset), whereas a value of zero indicates its absence.

Musical scales are inherently cyclic; the most widely employed systems across the world are based on twelve-tone structures (citation needed). Accordingly, scales in this paper are represented both geometrically and visually. A scale consisting of n potential notes is modeled as a circle with n distinct points uniformly distributed along its circumference. Since both Carnatic and Western music commonly employ twelve-tone systems (citation needed), the diagrams presented here are constructed with twelve equidistant points, each corresponding to a possible note in the scale.

Within such a framework, not all twelve notes are necessarily used. The subset of active notes is denoted by k , typically corresponding to the seven notes that form a given scale.

The arrangement and permutation of the seven fundamental *swaras* form the foundation of Carnatic music, giving rise to endless melodic possibilities. Although mathematics allows us to imagine as many as $7! = 5040$ theoretical combinations, only a small fraction—about 279—has found a place in practical usage. Among these, the structured set of 72 parent scales, known as *Mēlakarta ragas* or *Janaka ragas*, provides a systematic framework. Their formation follows strict rules: every *Mēlakarta* must include *Sa* and *Pa*, exactly one variant of *Ma*, one each from the pairs *Ri–Ga* and *Dha–Ni*, with the condition that *Ri* must precede *Ga* and *Dha* must precede *Ni*. This rule-bound construction yields precisely $2 \times 6 \times 6 = 72$ valid parent ragas. Each of these 72 serves as a backbone for countless *janya ragas*, where the beauty of Carnatic music emerges from the balance between combinatorial possibilities and the structural constraints that preserve identity.

Next, it is necessary to clarify certain key terms in Carnatic music, their meanings, and their approximate Western equivalents. The *Mēlakarta ragas* constitute the fundamental set of scales in Carnatic music. They function as *Janaka* (parent) ragas, from which other ragas, known as *Janya* ragas, are derived. The *Janya* ragas exhibit both combinatorial traits (rich *prayōgas*) and algebraic traits (rigid structural rules). Since the *Mēlakarta ragas* provide the structural foundation upon which Carnatic scales are built, they form the primary focus of consideration in this study.

3.2 Formation of Mēlakarta Ragas

The following rules and classifications govern the formation of a *Mēlakarta* raga:

1. *Sampūrṇa Ragas*: Every *Mēlakarta* raga must employ all seven *swaras* (notes) in both the ascending (*ārohaṇa*) and descending (*avarohaṇa*) movements.
2. *Upper Shadjam*: Each *Mēlakarta* raga must include the upper *shadjam* (the octave note).
3. *Symmetric Structure*: The *ārohaṇa* and *avarohaṇa* must utilize the same set of notes. This ensures a complete scalar framework, enabling maximal combinatorial possibilities—an aspect naturally aligned with the Erdős-deep analogy.
4. *Shāḍava Ragas*: These ragas employ only six *swaras* (hexatonic scales) in ascent or descent. The selective omission produces distinctive aesthetic flavors or moods. Although the algebraic scope is restricted, this limitation often heightens their expressive individuality.
5. *Auḍava Ragas*: These employ only five *swaras* (pentatonic scales). Despite their reduced scalar structure, typically associated with bright or majestic moods, the combinatorial richness of *prayōgas* (phrases) can still be considerable.
6. *Svarāntara Ragas*: This minimalistic category uses only four *swaras* (quadratonic scales). Under such stringent algebraic constraints, identity depends heavily on strict phraseology. Accordingly, they parallel the Winograd-deep analogy: a four-note framework lacks combinatorial expansion and instead relies on fixed patterns and *gamakas* (ornamentations) to sustain its distinctiveness.
7. *Vakra Ragas*: These incorporate a zig-zag (*vakra*) progression, deviating from strict sequential order by skipping or oscillating between notes. Their identity derives from these fixed zig-zag patterns rather than from the note set itself. This structural rigidity resonates with the Winograd-deep analogy, where identity arises from non-negotiable navigational constraints on *swaras*.
8. *Varjya Ragas*: In these ragas, one or more notes are deliberately omitted (*varjyam*) in either ascent or descent. Such omissions establish distinct moods and enhance characteristic recognition, though at the cost of reduced scalar flexibility.
9. *Bhāṣāṅga Ragas*: These primarily draw upon their parent *Mēlakarta* scale but incorporate *anya swaras* (foreign notes) from outside the parent framework. The inclusion of these external notes enriches the expressive palette of the raga, adding contrast, surprise, and unique emotional color (*bhāva*). *Bhāṣāṅga* ragas may thus be regarded as “hybrids,” embodying both Erdős-like (combinatorial expansion) and Winograd-like (algebraic rigidity) deepness: the scalar space is broadened by foreign notes, yet their application remains constrained to precise *prayōgas*.

The *Mēlakarta* system encompasses twelve semitones. A comparison between these semitones and their Western counterparts is presented below.

Figure 1: Mēlakarta chart

The 72 *Mēlakarta* ragas are systematically organized into 12 groups known as *chakras*, each comprising six ragas. Within a given *chakra*, the scales differ only in their D (*dhavata*) and N (*nishada*) notes, whereas variation across *chakras* arises from the specific assignment of the other *swaras*. Ragas within this scheme are identified using the *Kaṭapayādi Sūtra*, a classical Sanskrit mnemonic system in which digits are encoded by syllables or letters. In the Carnatic tradition, this system assigns canonical numbers to the 72 *Mēlakarta* ragas. Specifically, the first two syllables of a raga’s name encode digits, and these digits determine the raga’s position in the *Mēlakarta* enumeration.

From a mathematical standpoint, the *Kaṭapayādi* system exhibits two complementary structural properties. On the encoding side (syllables \rightarrow digits), the mapping is highly non-unique: multiple syllables correspond to the same digit, leading to a combinatorial explosion of possible encodings. This feature may be regarded as “Erdős-deep,” reflecting combinatorial richness and structural abundance. On the decoding side (number \rightarrow scale structure), the mapping is algebraically rigid: once the *Mēlakarta* number is fixed, the corresponding *sampūrṇa* scale—with its specific choices of *rsabha/gandhara* (R/G), *madhyama* (M), and *dhavata/nisada* (D/N)—is uniquely determined. This feature may be characterized as “Winograd-deep,” emphasizing algebraic determinism and structural rigidity.

कटपयादि संख्या - kaTapayAdi for Melakarta Ragam Names & Numbers									
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0
क	ख	ग	घ	ङ	च	छ	ज	झ	ञ
ट	ठ	ड	ढ	ण	त	थ	द	ध	न
प	फ	ब	भ	म					
य	र	ल	व	श	ष	स	ह		
ka	kha	ga	gha	nga	cha	Cha	ja	Jha	nya
Ta	Tha	Da	Dha	Na	ta	tha	da	dha	na
pa	pha	ba	bha	ma					
ya	ra	la	va	sha	Sha	sa	ha		

Figure 2: Kaṭapayādi system

Thus, the Kaṭapayādi system embodies a duality: the naming process reflects combinatorial depth (Erdős-deep), while the structural realization of ragas reflects algebraic depth (Winograd-deep). This yields two axes of complexity:

1. **Combinatorial richness:** how many different legal *sangatis* (phrases, variations) can be formed.
2. **Algebraic/structural rigidity:** how strongly the identity depends on fixed algebraic relationships (certain *swaras* pairs, *gamaka* rules, *vivadi* handling).

Erdős-deep ragas derive their complexity primarily from the combinatorial richness of permissible melodic phrases rather than from strict structural or algebraic constraints. These are typically popular *sampūrṇa* ragas such as *Śaṅkarābharanam* (29), *Kalyāṇi* (65), *Kharaharapriya* (22), and *Harikāmbhōji* (28). They give rise to a large number of *janya* ragas (derivatives) and are extensively employed in *kṛtis* (compositions). The essential feature of such ragas is that the combinatorial space of valid phrases grows rapidly with phrase length: almost any sequence of notes (within the defining rules) can still be perceived as belonging to the raga. This expressive freedom provides fertile ground for *manōdharmā* (improvisation) in *ālāpana*, *nēraṇa*, and *swara-kalpana*. No shallow or short-memory model can adequately capture their identity, as it is distributed across a large space of possible *prayōgas*. For example, *Śaṅkarābharanam* is closely aligned with the Western major scale, *Kalyāṇi* serves as an auspicious and foundational framework for *ālāpana* and *varṇams*, and *Kharaharapriya*, though often associated with pathos, supports a vast array of *sangati* possibilities. In this sense, Erdős-deep ragas embody depth through combinatorial abundance and distributed identity.

By contrast, Winograd-deep ragas derive their depth from rigid structural and algebraic dependencies. These include many *vivadi mēlas* (e.g., *Kanakāṅgi* 1, *Tānarūpi* 6, *Rasikapriya* 72) as well as certain *vakra* or *varjya janyas* such as *Sahānā*, *Bhairavī*, and *Abhōgi*. In these ragas, identity is determined by specific *gamakas*, compulsory zig-zag progressions, or precise interrelations among *swaras*. If such structural rules are relaxed or violated, the raga's identity collapses. The scope for combinatorial variation is comparatively limited, but the resulting beauty is one of algebraic precision, where depth arises from strict dependency relations. For instance:

Tōdi (8): the treatment of *Ri-Ga* requires heavy *kampita gamaka*; in functional terms, *Ga* is dependent on *Ri*.

Śubhapanthuvarālī (45): characteristic *prayōgas* function as structural invariants that cannot be altered without loss of identity.

Such dependencies may be viewed as algebraic equations, where one *swara* forces the behavior of another. Their representation requires deep algebraic circuits, in the style of Winograd-deep systems. Hence, Winograd-deep rāgas exhibit depth through structural rigidity and algebraic determinism, rather than combinatorial expansion.

In summary, Erdős-deep rāgas resemble expansive canvases, where depth emerges from a combinatorial explosion of permissible phrases, while Winograd-deep rāgas resemble carefully sculpted forms, where depth arises from the rigidity of structural and algebraic constraints.

3.3 Computation

To compute deepness for the ragas, the key step is understanding the definitions of Winograd-deep and Erdős-deep. Based on these, we wrote a Python program to accelerate the process, since the depth definitions provide the mathematical foundation necessary for an algorithmic test.

Winograd-deep:

```

from collections import defaultdict
from itertools import combinations

def circular_distance(a, b, n):
    """Return the circular distance between two indices on a circle of size n."""
    return min((b - a) % n, (a - b) % n)

def calculate_deepness(rhythm):
    n = len(rhythm)
    onsets = [i for i, beat in enumerate(rhythm) if beat == 1]
    k = len(onsets)

    if k < 2:
        print("Not enough onsets to compute deepness.")
        return False

    # Count all distances between pairs of onsets
    distance_counts = defaultdict(int)

    for i, j in combinations(onsets, 2):
        dist = circular_distance(i, j, n)
        distance_counts[dist] += 1

    # Remove distance 0 and sort distances
    if 0 in distance_counts:
        del distance_counts[0]

    frequency_of_counts = defaultdict(int)
    for count in distance_counts.values():
        frequency_of_counts[count] += 1

```

```

    is_deep = len(frequency_of_counts) == (k - 1)

    return is_deep, dict(distance_counts), dict(frequency_of_counts)

# Example usage
rhythm = [1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1]
deep, distances, freqs = calculate_deepness(rhythm)

print("Is the rhythm deep?", deep)
print("Distance counts:", distances)
print("Frequency of counts:", freqs)

```

Erdős-deep:

```

from collections import defaultdict
from itertools import combinations

def circular_distance(a, b, n):
    """Return the circular distance between two indices on a circle of size n."""
    return min((b - a) % n, (a - b) % n)

def calculate_deepness_v2(rhythm):
    n = len(rhythm)
    onsets = [i for i, beat in enumerate(rhythm) if beat == 1]
    k = len(onsets)

    if k < 2:
        print("Not enough onsets to compute deepness.")
        return False

    # Count distances between every unique pair of onsets
    distance_counts = defaultdict(int)

    for i, j in combinations(onsets, 2):
        dist = circular_distance(i, j, n)
        if dist != 0: # ignore zero distances
            distance_counts[dist] += 1

    # Check if all counts are unique
    count_values = list(distance_counts.values())
    is_deep = len(count_values) == len(set(count_values)) # all counts must be unique

    return is_deep, dict(distance_counts)

# Example usage
rhythm = [1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1]
deep, distances = calculate_deepness_v2(rhythm)

```

```
print("Is the rhythm deep?", deep)
print("Distance counts:", distances)
```

We then applied this to all 72 *Mēlakarta* rāgas and created a spreadsheet recording the distances, multiplicities, and whether each scale is Winograd-deep and Erdős-deep.

	Raga	Carnatic	Western	Binary Representation	Winograd Deep	Distance counts	Multiplicity	Erdos Deep
1. Indu Chakra (All D and N combinations)								
1	Kanakāngi	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D b E b b F G A b B b b C	XXXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 4, 2: 3, 5: 5, 4: 4, 3: 3, 6: 2}	{4: 2, 3: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
2	Ratnāngi	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E b b F G A b B b C	XXXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 3, 2: 4, 5: 5, 4: 3, 6: 2, 3: 4}	{3: 2, 4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
3	Gānāmūrti	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E b b F G A b B C	XXXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 4, 2: 3, 5: 4, 4: 3, 6: 3, 3: 4}	{4: 3, 3: 3}	NO
4	Vānaspati	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E b b F G A b b C	XXXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 3, 2: 4, 5: 5, 3: 4, 4: 4, 6: 1}	{3: 1, 4: 3, 5: 1, 1: 1}	NO
5	Mānavati	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E b b F G A B C	XXXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 3, 2: 5, 5: 4, 3: 3, 4: 4, 6: 2}	{3: 2, 5: 1, 4: 2, 2: 1}	NO
6	Tānarūpi	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E b b F G A# B C	XXXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 4, 2: 4, 5: 4, 4: 3, 6: 2, 3: 4}	{4: 4, 3: 1, 2: 1}	NO
2. Netra Chakra (All G2 + Indu)								
7	Senāvati	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D b E b F G A b B b b C	XXOXOXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 3, 3: 3, 5: 4, 4: 5, 2: 4, 6: 2}	{3: 2, 4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
8	Hanumatodi	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E b F G A b B b C	XXOXOXOXXOXX	YES	{1: 2, 3: 4, 5: 6, 4: 3, 2: 5, 6: 1}	{2: 1, 4: 1, 6: 1, 3: 1, 5: 1, 1: 1}	YES
9	Dhenukā	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E b F G A b B C	XXOXOXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 3, 3: 3, 5: 4, 4: 5, 2: 4, 6: 2}	{3: 2, 4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
10	Nātakapriyā	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E b F G A b b C	XXOXOXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 2, 3: 4, 5: 4, 2: 5, 4: 4, 6: 2}	{2: 2, 4: 3, 5: 1}	NO
11	Kokilapriyā	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E b F G A B C	XXOXOXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 2, 3: 2, 5: 2, 2: 6, 4: 6, 6: 3}	{2: 3, 6: 2, 3: 1}	NO
12	Rūpavati	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E b F G A# B C	XXOXOXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 3, 3: 3, 5: 4, 2: 5, 4: 4, 6: 2}	{3: 2, 4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
3. Agni Chakra (All G3 + Indu)								
13	Gāyakapriyā	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D b E F G A b B b b C	XXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 4, 4: 6, 5: 4, 3: 4, 6: 1, 2: 2}	{4: 3, 6: 1, 1: 1, 2: 1}	NO
14	Vakulābharaṇam	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E F G A b B b C	XXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 3, 4: 4, 5: 4, 2: 3, 3: 5, 6: 2}	{3: 2, 4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
15	Māyāmājavagowla	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E F G A b B C	XXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 4, 4: 5, 5: 4, 3: 4, 6: 2, 2: 2}	{4: 3, 5: 1, 2: 2}	NO
16	Chakravākam	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E F G A b b C	XXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 3, 4: 4, 5: 4, 3: 5, 2: 3, 6: 2}	{3: 2, 4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
17	Sūryakāntam	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E F G A B C	XXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 3, 4: 5, 5: 4, 3: 3, 6: 2, 2: 4}	{3: 2, 5: 1, 4: 2, 2: 1}	NO
18	Hātakāmbari	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E F G A# B C	XXOXXOXXOXX	NO	{1: 4, 4: 3, 5: 4, 2: 3, 3: 4, 6: 3}	{4: 3, 3: 3}	NO
4. Veda Chakra (All R2, G2 + Indu)								
19	Jhankāradhvani	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D E b F G A b B b b C	XOXXOXOXXOXX	NO	{2: 4, 3: 4, 5: 5, 4: 3, 1: 3, 6: 2}	{4: 2, 5: 1, 3: 2, 2: 1}	NO
20	Naṭabhairavi	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D E b F G A b B b C	XOXXOXOXXOXX	YES	{2: 5, 3: 4, 5: 6, 4: 3, 1: 2, 6: 1}	{5: 1, 4: 1, 6: 1, 3: 1, 2: 1, 1: 1}	YES
21	Kīravāṇi	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D E b F G A b B C	XOXXOXOXXOXX	NO	{2: 3, 3: 5, 5: 4, 4: 4, 1: 3, 6: 2}	{3: 2, 5: 1, 4: 2, 2: 1}	NO
22	Kharaharapriyā	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D E b F G A b b C	XOXXOXOXXOXX	YES	{2: 5, 3: 4, 5: 6, 1: 2, 4: 3, 6: 1}	{5: 1, 4: 1, 6: 1, 2: 1, 3: 1, 1: 1}	YES
23	Gourīmanohari	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D E b F G A B C	XOXXOXOXXOXX	NO	{2: 5, 3: 4, 5: 4, 1: 2, 4: 4, 6: 2}	{5: 1, 4: 3, 2: 2}	NO
24	Varunapriyā	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D E b F G A# B C	XOXXOXOXXOXX	NO	{2: 4, 3: 4, 5: 5, 1: 3, 4: 4, 6: 1}	{4: 3, 5: 1, 3: 1, 1: 1}	NO

	Raga	Carnatic	Western	Binary Representation	Winograd Deep	Distance counts	Multiplicity	Erdos Deep
5. Bana Chakra (All R2, G3 + Indu)								
25	Māraṅjanī	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D E F G A ♭ B ♭ ♭ C	X O X O X X O X X X O O X	NO	{2: 4, 4: 4, 5: 5, 3: 4, 6: 1, 1: 3}	{4: 3, 5: 1, 1: 1, 3: 1}	NO
26	Chārukesi	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D E F G A ♭ B ♭ ♭ C	X O X O X X O X X O X O X	NO	{2: 5, 4: 4, 5: 4, 3: 4, 6: 2, 1: 2}	{5: 1, 4: 3, 2: 2}	NO
27	Sarasāṅgi	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₃ Ś	C D E F G A ♭ B C	X O X O X X O X X O O X X	NO	{2: 3, 4: 4, 5: 4, 1: 3, 3: 5, 6: 2}	{3: 2, 4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
28	Harikāmbhōji	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₂ N ₂ Ś	C D E F G A B ♭ C	X O X O X X O X X O X O X	YES	{2: 5, 4: 3, 5: 6, 3: 4, 1: 2, 6: 1}	{5: 1, 3: 1, 6: 1, 4: 1, 2: 1, 1: 1}	YES
29	Dhīraśankarābharāṇam	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₂ N ₃ Ś	C D E F G A B C	X O X O X X O X X O X O X	YES	{2: 5, 4: 3, 5: 6, 3: 4, 1: 2, 6: 1}	{5: 1, 3: 1, 6: 1, 4: 1, 2: 1, 1: 1}	YES
30	Nāganandini	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₃ N ₃ Ś	C D E F G A # B C	X O X O X X O X O O X X X	NO	{2: 4, 4: 3, 5: 5, 1: 3, 3: 4, 6: 2}	{4: 2, 3: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
6. Rutu Chakra (All R3, G3 + Indu)								
31	Yāgapriyā	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D # E F G A ♭ B ♭ ♭ C	X O O X X X O X X X O O X	NO	{3: 4, 4: 5, 5: 4, 1: 4, 2: 3, 6: 1}	{4: 3, 5: 1, 3: 1, 1: 1}	NO
32	Rāgavardhini	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D # E F G A ♭ B ♭ ♭ C	X O O X X X O X X O X O X	NO	{3: 4, 4: 4, 5: 5, 2: 4, 1: 3, 6: 1}	{4: 3, 5: 1, 3: 1, 1: 1}	NO
33	Gāṅgeyabhūṣaṇi	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₁ N ₃ Ś	C D # E F G A ♭ B C	X O O X X X O X X O O X X	NO	{3: 4, 4: 6, 5: 4, 1: 4, 2: 2, 6: 1}	{4: 3, 6: 1, 2: 1, 1: 1}	NO
34	Vāgadhiśvari	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₂ N ₂ Ś	C D # E F G A B ♭ C	X O O X X X O X X O X O X	NO	{3: 4, 4: 3, 5: 5, 2: 4, 1: 3, 6: 2}	{4: 2, 3: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
35	Śūlini	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₂ N ₃ Ś	C D # E F G A B C	X O O X X X O X X O X O X	NO	{3: 3, 4: 5, 5: 4, 1: 3, 2: 4, 6: 2}	{3: 2, 5: 1, 4: 2, 2: 1}	NO
36	Chalanāṭa	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₁ P D ₃ N ₃ Ś	C D # E F G A # B C	X O O X X X O X O O X X X	NO	{3: 3, 4: 4, 5: 5, 2: 3, 1: 4, 6: 2}	{3: 2, 4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1}	NO
7. Rishi Chakra (All M2 + Indu)								
37	Sālagam	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ ♭ F # G A ♭ B ♭ ♭ C	X X X O O O X X X X O O X	NO	{1: 5, 2: 3, 6: 3, 5: 5, 4: 3, 3: 2}	{5: 2, 3: 3, 2: 1}	NO
38	Jalārnavam	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ ♭ F # G A ♭ B ♭ C	X X X O O O X X X O X O X	NO	{1: 4, 2: 4, 6: 3, 5: 4, 4: 3, 2: 2}	{4: 4, 3: 1, 2: 1}	NO
39	Jhālavārāli	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₃ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ ♭ F # G A ♭ B C	X X X O O O X X X O O X X	NO	{1: 5, 2: 3, 6: 3, 5: 5, 4: 3, 3: 2}	{5: 2, 3: 3, 2: 1}	NO
40	Navanītam	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₂ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ ♭ F # G A B ♭ C	X X X O O O X X X O X O X	NO	{1: 4, 2: 3, 6: 2, 5: 4, 3: 4, 4: 4}	{4: 4, 3: 1, 2: 1}	NO
41	Pāvani	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₃ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ ♭ F # G A B C	X X X O O O X X X O X O X	NO	{1: 4, 2: 4, 6: 2, 5: 5, 3: 3, 4: 3}	{4: 2, 2: 1, 5: 1, 3: 2}	NO
42	Raghupriyā	S R ₁ G ₁ M ₂ P D ₃ N ₃ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ ♭ F # G A # B C	X X X O O O X X O O X X X	NO	{1: 5, 2: 3, 6: 2, 5: 4, 3: 3, 4: 4}	{5: 1, 3: 2, 2: 1, 4: 2}	NO
8. Vasu Chakra (All G2, M2 + Indu)								
43	Gavāmbhodi	S R ₁ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ F # G A ♭ B ♭ ♭ C	X X O X O O X X X X O O X	NO	{1: 4, 3: 4, 6: 3, 5: 4, 4: 3, 2: 3}	{4: 3, 3: 3}	NO
44	Bhavapriyā	S R ₁ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ F # G A ♭ B ♭ C	X X O X O O X X X O X O X	NO	{1: 3, 3: 4, 6: 2, 5: 5, 4: 3, 2: 4}	{3: 2, 4: 2, 2: 1, 5: 1}	NO
45	Śubhapantuvarāli	S R ₁ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₃ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ F # G A ♭ B C	X X O X O O X X X O O X X	NO	{1: 4, 3: 3, 6: 2, 5: 5, 4: 4, 2: 3}	{4: 2, 3: 2, 2: 1, 5: 1}	NO
46	Shaḍvidamārgini	S R ₁ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₂ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ F # G A B ♭ C	X X O X O O X X X O X O X	NO	{1: 3, 3: 6, 6: 3, 5: 3, 2: 3, 4: 3}	{3: 5, 6: 1}	NO
47	Suvarnāṅgi	S R ₁ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₃ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ F # G A B C	X X O X O O X X X O X O X	NO	{1: 3, 3: 4, 6: 3, 5: 3, 2: 4, 4: 4}	{3: 3, 4: 3}	NO
48	Divyamaṅgi	S R ₁ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₃ N ₃ Ś	C D ♭ E ♭ F # G A # B C	X X O X O O X X O O X X X	NO	{1: 4, 3: 4, 6: 2, 5: 4, 2: 3, 4: 4}	{4: 4, 2: 1, 3: 1}	NO

	Raga	Carnatic	Western	Binary Representation	Winograd Deep	Distance counts	Multiplicity	Erdos Deep
9. Brahma Chakra (All G3, M2 + Indu)								
49	Dhavaḷāmbari	S R ₁ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D b E F# G A b B b b C	X X O O X O X X X X O O X	NO	{1: 4, 4: 4, 6: 2, 5: 4, 3: 4, 2: 3}	{4: 4, 2: 1, 3: 1}	NO
50	Nāmanārāyaṇi	S R ₁ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D b E F# G A b B b C	X X O O X O X X X O X O X	NO	{1: 3, 4: 4, 6: 3, 5: 3, 2: 4, 3: 4}	{3: 3, 4: 3}	NO
51	Kāmavardhini	S R ₁ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₃ Ś	C D b E F# G A b B C	X X O O X O X X X O O X X	NO	{1: 4, 4: 4, 6: 2, 5: 5, 3: 3, 2: 3}	{4: 2, 2: 1, 5: 1, 3: 2}	NO
52	Rāmapiyā	S R ₁ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₂ Ś	C D b E F# G A B b C	X X O O X O X X O X X O X	NO	{1: 3, 4: 3, 6: 3, 5: 3, 3: 6, 2: 3}	{3: 5, 6: 1}	NO
53	Gamanāśrama	S R ₁ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₃ Ś	C D b E F# G A B C	X X O O X O X X O X O X X	NO	{1: 3, 4: 3, 6: 2, 5: 5, 3: 4, 2: 4}	{3: 2, 2: 1, 5: 1, 4: 2}	NO
54	Viśvambari	S R ₁ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₃ N ₃ Ś	C D b E F# G A# B C	X X O O X O X X O O X X X	NO	{1: 4, 4: 3, 6: 3, 5: 4, 2: 3, 3: 4}	{4: 3, 3: 3}	NO
10. Diśi Chakra (All R2, G2, M2 + Indu)								
55	Śāmaḷāṅgi	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D E b F# G A b B b b C	X O X X O O X X X X O O X	NO	{2: 3, 3: 4, 6: 3, 5: 4, 4: 3, 1: 4}	{3: 3, 4: 3}	NO
56	Śānmukhapriyā	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D E b F# G A b B b C	X O X X O O X X X O X O X	NO	{2: 4, 3: 3, 6: 2, 5: 4, 4: 5, 1: 3}	{4: 2, 3: 2, 2: 1, 5: 1}	NO
57	Simhendramadhyama	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₃ Ś	C D E b F# G A b B C	X O X X O O X X X O O X X	NO	{2: 2, 3: 4, 6: 2, 5: 4, 4: 5, 1: 4}	{2: 2, 4: 3, 5: 1}	NO
58	Hemavati	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₂ Ś	C D E b F# G A B b C	X O X X O O X X O X X O X	NO	{2: 3, 3: 5, 6: 2, 5: 4, 1: 3, 4: 4}	{3: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1, 4: 2}	NO
59	Dharmavati	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₃ Ś	C D E b F# G A B C	X O X X O O X X O X O X X	NO	{2: 3, 3: 5, 6: 2, 5: 4, 1: 3, 4: 4}	{3: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1, 4: 2}	NO
60	Nītimati	S R ₂ G ₂ M ₂ P D ₃ N ₃ Ś	C D E b F# G A# B C	X O X X O O X X O O X X X	NO	{2: 2, 3: 4, 6: 1, 5: 4, 1: 4, 4: 6}	{2: 1, 4: 3, 1: 1, 6: 1}	NO
11. Rudra Chakra (All R2, G3, M2 + Indu)								
61	Kāntāmaṇi	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D E F# G A b B b b C	X O X O X O X X X X O O X	NO	{2: 5, 4: 4, 6: 2, 5: 4, 3: 3, 1: 3}	{5: 1, 4: 2, 2: 1, 3: 2}	NO
62	Riśabhapriyā	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D E F# G A b B b C	X O X O X O X X X O X O X	NO	{2: 6, 4: 6, 6: 3, 5: 2, 3: 2, 1: 2}	{6: 2, 3: 1, 2: 3}	NO
63	Latāṅgi	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₃ Ś	C D E F# G A b B C	X O X O X O X X X O O X X	NO	{2: 4, 4: 5, 6: 2, 5: 4, 1: 3, 3: 3}	{4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1, 3: 2}	NO
64	Vāchaspati	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₂ Ś	C D E F# G A B b C	X O X O X O X X O X X O X	NO	{2: 5, 4: 4, 6: 2, 5: 4, 3: 4, 1: 2}	{5: 1, 4: 3, 2: 2}	NO
65	Mechakalyāni	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₃ Ś	C D E F# G A B C	X O X O X O X X O X O X X	YES	{2: 5, 4: 3, 6: 1, 5: 6, 3: 4, 1: 2}	{5: 1, 3: 1, 1: 1, 6: 1, 4: 1, 2: 1}	YES
66	Chitrāmbari	S R ₂ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₃ N ₃ Ś	C D E F# G A# B C	X O X O X O X X O O X X X	NO	{2: 4, 4: 5, 6: 2, 5: 4, 1: 3, 3: 3}	{4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1, 3: 2}	NO
12. Aditya Chakra (All R3, G3, M2 + Indu)								
67	Sucharitrā	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₁ Ś	C D# E F# G A b B b b C	X O O X X O X X X X O O X	NO	{3: 5, 4: 4, 6: 2, 5: 3, 1: 4, 2: 3}	{5: 1, 4: 2, 2: 1, 3: 2}	NO
68	Jyoti svarupini	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₂ Ś	C D# E F# G A b B b C	X O O X X O X X X O X O X	NO	{3: 4, 4: 5, 6: 2, 5: 3, 2: 4, 1: 3}	{4: 2, 5: 1, 2: 1, 3: 2}	NO
69	Dhāthuvardhani	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₁ N ₃ Ś	C D# E F# G A b B C	X O O X X O X X X O O X X	NO	{3: 4, 4: 6, 6: 1, 5: 4, 1: 4, 2: 2}	{4: 3, 6: 1, 1: 1, 2: 1}	NO
70	Nāsikābhūṣaṇi	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₂ Ś	C D# E F# G A B b C	X O O X X O X X O X X O X	NO	{3: 6, 4: 3, 6: 3, 5: 3, 2: 3, 1: 3}	{6: 1, 3: 5}	NO
71	Kōsalam	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₂ N ₃ Ś	C D# E F# G A B C	X O O X X O X X O X O X X	NO	{3: 5, 4: 4, 6: 2, 5: 4, 1: 3, 2: 3}	{5: 1, 4: 2, 2: 1, 3: 2}	NO
72	Rasikapriyā	S R ₃ G ₃ M ₂ P D ₃ N ₃ Ś	C D# E F# G A# B C	X O O X X O X X O O X X X	NO	{3: 4, 4: 5, 6: 2, 5: 4, 2: 2, 1: 4}	{4: 3, 5: 1, 2: 2}	NO

Figure 3: Mēlakarta rāgas with features

One key observation was that the only scales that were both Winograd-deep and Erdős-deep were the major scales also present in Western music, such as the C major scale. Furthermore, there were no scales that were only Erdős-deep; all such scales were simultaneously Winograd-deep and Erdős-deep. Following this data collection, we realized that we did not have sufficient knowledge of Carnatic music—its expectations and rules—to judge whether further conclusions could be drawn from these data. Hence, we decided to interview and seek an expert’s help in the field to better understand the results at hand.

Furthermore, we also wished to investigate other types of scales in Western music—such as minor and pentatonic—and to see whether a relationship exists there, even if not in Carnatic music, in order to determine whether only major scales, or potentially other types of scales as well, can be Erdős-deep and Winograd-deep. Some of this analysis can also be found in [1].

4 Conclusion

Carnatic music, though rooted in aesthetic and spiritual expression, reveals striking parallels with mathematical notions of depth. On the one hand, rāgas that allow vast melodic freedom, such as *Śaṅkarābharanam*, *Kalyāṇi*, and *Kharaharapriyā*, embody Erdős-deepness: their richness arises from combinatorial explosion, with innumerable valid *prayōgas* and countless *janya* rāgas branching from them. On the other hand, rāgas defined by strict structural rules, such as *Tōḍi*, *Kanakāṅgi*, and *Śubhapanthuvarāli*, exemplify Winograd-deepness, where depth lies not in variety but in algebraic rigidity, *gamaka* constraints, and precise phraseology that cannot be violated without losing identity. Hybrid cases, like *Bhāṣāṅga* rāgas, combine both: they expand the scale space by permitting *anya svaras* (Erdős aspect) while simultaneously binding them to exact contexts (Winograd aspect).

Thus, Carnatic music illustrates a profound duality: its creative power arises both from combinatorial abundance and from structural necessity. Just as Erdős’ combinatorial arguments and Winograd’s algebraic lower bounds capture different facets of complexity in mathematics, the rāgas of Carnatic music show that true depth arises from the interplay of freedom and constraint, making the system both vast and precise at once.

References

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